

Association of COVID-19 with Vaccination Status Among Health Science College Students, University of Duhok, 2022

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Abstract

Background and objectives: During the Covid-19 pandemic the community adopts several preventive measures such as; hand washing, wearing masks and social distancing whereas acquiring vaccines was considered to be the most efficient preventive measure. Therefore, this study was designed to calculate its association among health care students. **Methods:** A 310 students from college of health sciences/ university of Duhok participated through answering an online questioner for identifying the vaccine coverage, its efficacy through (RR) measurement and the hesitancy causes. **Results:** A high proportion of participants 231 out of 310 (74.5%) were registered for analysis, the vaccination coverage was low (45%) meanwhile the vaccine hesitancy was found to be high (55%) and the main cause was the side effects of the vaccines. Among 46 participants who experienced COVID-19 disease, 35(76.08%) were among those who not get vaccinated while only 11 (23.9%) were among vaccinated students; four from 46(8.6%) students were among those who got the disease before two weeks from vaccination while 7 (15.21%) were among those whose experienced the disease after two weeks from vaccination. The risk ratio or relative risk among who's got two doses or more of vaccination was estimated to be (0.068) which is lower that among none vaccinated or vaccinated with one dose (0.164). The overall relative risk among vaccinated students was 0.414 CI: (0.183 – 0.936) with a P value < 0.05 which was statistically significant as well as the risk of infection was lowest (0.07) among who wear masks always while it was highest (0.17)

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among who wear masks occasionally. **Conclusion:** Health students are advised and encouraged to receive COVID-19 vaccination as well as to wear masks always.

Introduction

The Coronavirus disease-19 (COVID-19) firstly reported in Wuhan city, Hubei province, China in December 2019. Soon later the morbidity quickly reaches more than 2 39.4 million with mortality over 4.8 million, in response, several vaccines have been tested and granted emergency use authorization [1].

The causative agent was the genus Corona viruses which were firstly described in 1966 by Tyrell and Bynoe who cultivated the viruses from patients with common colds [2]. Under microscope the virus showed surface projections with single-stranded large RNA [3]. The alpha and beta virus genera only infect the infect mammals including humans [4]. Within the last twenty years reports showed three novel coronavirus transmissions to humans leading to severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) disease [5].

The first outbreak was SARS-CoV in Guangdong, China in November 2002 [6] while the second was the Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) in Saudi Arabia in 2012 [7]. The coronaviruses spread quickly through droplets during breathing, coughing, sneezing, or speaking. On 24 February 2020 the WHO declared that it has the possibility to cause a pandemic outbreak [9,10,11]. Subsequently, on 11 March 2020 the WHO declared the COVID-19 as a pandemic [12].

The availability of vaccine was essential to control the spread of the disease, but it was not more important than hesitancy which became a global phenomenon mainly due to the safety of the vaccine [13] and the hesitancy was more prevalent in poor countries than in rich countries [14,15].

After 2-14 days of exposure to the virus, the affected people might experience mild to severe symptoms such

as fever, dry cough and fatigue, less common symptoms are loss of taste or smell, sore throat, headache, muscle or joint pain, different types of skin rash, nausea or vomiting, diarrhea and chills or dizziness [16]. Several antiviral and anti-malarial drugs had been tried to reduce the virus transmission [17] but the more efficient measure was the development of vaccines to induce viral immunity [18]. Until July 2021 there were 184 COVID-19 vaccines in pre-clinical development, 105 in clinical development, and 18 vaccines approved for emergency use [19]. During the first of COVID-19 pandemic, the routine immunization coverage regressed because of their fear and hesitancy from different causes especially the health care workers and personnel are at higher risk of infection and their hesitancy to get vaccination led to exposure to a higher risk if they didn't get vaccinated [20,21].

Because of the vague fate of the disease, most countries all over the world started procuring huge number of doses of different COVID-19 vaccines for their communities. Therefore, the vaccine efficacies which refers to the degree to which a vaccine prevents sever symptoms or hospitalization were seen vital to be measured by calculating their relative risk (RR). The major risk in front of getting herd immunity is hesitancy in acquiring vaccination whereas vaccines appear to be the most efficient measure of controlling the pandemic [22,23,24]. Vaccination hesitancy was reported in more than 90% of countries whereas it is essential to achieve high COVID-19 vaccination acceptance rates among medical students and health care workers to provide recommendations and counseling vaccine hesitant population [25].

Figure 1: The Study Design

Patients and Methods

A questioner composed of (10) questions to be answered by participant was prepared and it was three

sections: Section A, composed of general information such as age, sex, class and department. Section B was about vaccination status (acquiring status and doses),

experiencing and timing of Covid-19 disease and wearing face mask status while section C was about health belief model and the causes of vaccine refusal. The study was conducted within three months (from February 2022 - May 2022), questionnaire was distributed online via an QR code web link over 310 students through a kobo Toolbox form software program to be answered within two weeks. The study design and groups of participants are declared in figure 1.

Statistical Analyses

An Excel spreadsheet and Statistical Package for Social Studies, SPSS (IBM V 23) software were used to calculate the proportion of univariant variables to summarize the descriptive data and to calculate the risk among the students. The P value of <0.05, relative risk (RR) of not equal to one and a 95% CI not included one, the association were considered statistically significant. The relative risk was measure through following equation:

$$Relative\ Risk\ (RR) = \frac{Risk\ of\ Covid-19\ among\ vaccinated\ with\ \geq 2\ doses}{Risk\ of\ Covid-19\ among\ non-vaccinated\ or\ vaccinated\ with\ < 2\ doses} \tag{1}$$

Results

Table 1 showed that response rate among different classes of participants. This study reported overall rate of response to participation 231 out of 310 (74.5%), the highest 96.8%

was within first-year students of Anesthesia Science department while the lowest 54.1% was among second year’s students of same department.

Table 1: Cohort of Participation Among Different Classes of Participants

Department / Grade	Admin. Lists	Participants	%
Anesthesia science	127	93	73.2
Anesthesia science First Year	31	30	96.8
Anesthesia science Second Year	37	20	54.1
Anesthesia science Third Year	35	29	82.9
Anesthesia science Fourth Year	24	14	58.3
Medical Laboratory sciences	183	138	75.4
Medical Laboratory sciences First Year	50	30	60.0
Medical Laboratory sciences Second Year	59	48	81.4
Medical Laboratory sciences Third Year	49	39	79.6
Medical Laboratory sciences Fourth Year	25	21	84.0
Grand Total	310	231	74.5

Table 2 shows the vaccination status of the students with any type of SARS-CoV-2 vaccines. The current study found that only one hundred and four (45.02%) of students were vaccinated. Only eighty

one (35.06%) of vaccinated students had received two doses of vaccine

Table 2: The Rate of Vaccination, Experiencing Covid-19 and Association of Vaccination with Covid-19 Disease

Variables	Response	N	%
Are you vaccinated with any type of SARS-CoV-2 vaccines?	Yes	104	45.02
	No	127	54.98
How many vaccine doses you received?	One dose	23	9.96
	Two doses	81	35.06
	Three doses	0	0.00
	Not vaccinated	127	54.98
Did you ever get, or experience COVID-19 confirmed by PCR?	Yes	46	19.91
	No	185	80.09
If Yes (get or experience COVID-19), when?	After 14 days from the second dose of the vaccine.	7	3.03
	Within 14 days from any dose of vaccine.	4	1.73
	Before being vaccinated or never being vaccinated	35	15.15
	Not got or experience COVID-19	185	80.09

If you get or experience COVID-19, did you be hospitalized?	Yes	3	6.52
	No	43	93.48
Total		231	100

Table 3 shows individual measure of wearing mask taken by the students.

The results of this study showed highest proportion of participants (49.78%) sometimes wear masks in indoor and the lowest (5.63%) was among who never wear mask.

Table 4 clarify the perceived barriers of COVID-19 vaccination among the unvaccinated students.

Results in the current study reported that common rejection barriers for hesitancy to get vaccination among participants were their side effects, efficacy, safety, social media rumors, confident etc. while the most common causes of vaccination rejection were distrust and safety (24.4%) and (19.7%) respectively. Table five shows the risk after being vaccinated and by socio demographic characteristics and wearing masks.

Table 3: The Rate of Individual Wearing Mask Habit Among the Students

Variable	Response	N	Percentage
Do you wear mask in indoor (e.g., The lecture’s Hall, the Lab rooms) or indoor gatherings (example: in the cafeteria, during social, religious, or sport events)?	Never	13	5.63
	Sometimes (Appropriate using)	115	49.78
	Always (it means the appropriate using of the mask)	103	44.59

Table 4: The Rate of Perceived Barriers of COVID-19 Vaccination Among Student

Variables	Response	N	Percentage
Perceived barriers of COVID-19 vaccination	I heard from social media that the vaccine is not good	24	24.4%
	I am concern about the safety of the COVID-19 vaccination	25	19.7%
	I am not confident in using COVID-19 vaccine	14	18.9%
	I am concern about the efficacy of the COVID-19 vaccination	16	12.6%
	I am already experienced COVID-19, I don’t need the vaccine	11	11.0%
	Worry the possible side-effects of COVID-19 vaccination would interfere with my usual activities	31	8.7%
	I am concern of my affordability of getting the COVID-19 vaccination	3	2.4%
	I am concern of the faulty/fake COVID-19 vaccine	3	2.4%
	I am Pregnant worry about my fetous	0	0.0%

Table 5: Rate of Risk of Covid-19 After Being Vaccinated, by Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Wearing Masks

Variables	Response	Got Covid-19	Not Got Covid-19	Total	Risk (Incidence proportion)
Total		28	203	231	0.12
Gender	Male	6	43	49	0.12
	Female	22	160	182	0.12
Department	Medical Lab Sciences	19	119	138	0.14
	Anesthesia Science	9	84	93	0.10
Grade	First	7	53	60	0.12
	Second	8	60	68	0.12
	Third	8	60	68	0.12
	Fourth	5	30	35	0.14
Do you wear mask in indoor (e.g., The lecture’s Hall, the Lab rooms) or indoor gatherings (example: in the cafeteria, during social, religious, or sport events)?	Never	2	11	13	0.15
	Sometimes (Appropriate using)	19	96	115	0.17
	Always (it means the appropriate using of the mask)	7	96	103	0.07

This study found little but not significant differences in risks reported which was more by 0.04 among medical lab students, as well as the risk to get Covid-19 are more by 0.02 among fourth grade students. The statistically significant differences reported was seen only between students who sometimes wear masks 0.17 (the highest)

and among those students who always wear masks was 0.07 (the lowest).

Table six shows the risk of Covid-19 among vaccinated students with two or more vaccine doses and none vaccinated students or vaccinated with one dose.

Table 6. Risk Ratio of Covid-19 after 14-day from the Second Dose of SARS-CoV-2 Vaccination

Exposure (vaccination)	Outcome (Covid-19)			Risk (95% CI)	Risk (AR) %	P Value Significant at > 0.05	Risk Ratio
	Yes	No	Total				
Yes (=> 2 doses of the vaccine)	7	96	103	0.068	6.8	.026	0.414
No (not vaccinated or vaccinated with < 2 doses)	21	107	128	0.164	16.4		
Total	28	203	231	0.121	12.1		

The risk estimated in this study among who get two or more vaccines was (0.068) while the risk of Covid-19 among unvaccinated students or vaccinated with less than 2 doses was (0.164).

The overall Attack Rate of Covid-19 among the vaccinated students was 12.1%, while the Risk Ratio or Relative Risk estimated was 0.414 (95% CI: (0.183 – 0.936) with a P value 0.026.

Discussion

The rate of participation reported in this study was 74.5% was fortunately higher those had been seen among other researches in other countries such as; from 21144 health and none health Colombian citizens (6.7%) [26], within 304 Texas health staff (26.6%) [27], between 5374 health staff Slovakiens (22.85%) [28], out of 1894 health science Spanish students (58.78%) [29], among 742 Japanese medical students (66.8%) [30] and Hong Kong from 1660 nurses (72%) [31].

The current study found that rate of vaccination was (45.02%) among students which unfortunately is higher only from those results reported in; Colombia among 21144 health students (21%) [26] and China among 806 nurses (40%) [32] while it was lower than results seen in most other countries such as those seen in; Hong Kong among 1660 nurses (46%) [31], England among 6952440 citizens (57.9%) [33], Palestine among 1018 health staff (66.5%) [34], Slovakia among 5374 medical students (71.7%) [28], Israel among 1942 health care workers (75%) [35], France among 2047 different health care workers (76.9%) [36], Italy among 735 health care students (86.1%) [37], Japan among 742 university medical students (89.1%) [30], USA among 304 health staff (95.1%) [27] and Spain among health science students (97.8%) [29].

Only eighty-one (35.06%) of vaccinated students had received two doses of vaccines which was much lower

than rate reported in England (74.1%) [33]. Forty six out of 231 respondents (15.15%) experienced the disease whereas thirty-five (76.08%) of them were among not vaccinated students.

The current study reported that the most common causes of vaccination rejection were distrust and safety (24.4%) and (19.7%) respectively, this result was different from that was reported among nurses in Hong Kong China which was the efficacy (low acceptance 40%) [32] whereas the most common cause of hesitancy among health teams in Israel was the fear from getting the disease (acceptance 78%) [35] as well as the commonest causes of hesitancy among nurses in Hong Kong China in another study was younger ages and weak compliance (46%) [31]. Other hesitancy causes found in France among different health staffs was to be a nurse (acceptance 64.7%) [36]. In Colombia low acceptance rate among health and no health groups was due to none being health staff (79%) [26]. Another hesitancy cause reported in Palestine among different health staffs was the efficacy and people believe in natural immunity rather than vaccination (acceptance rate 66.5%) [34].

This study found that there were no statistically significant differences in incidence rate between both males and females. There were little but not significant differences in risks reported which was more by 0.04 among medical lab students, as well as the risk to get Covid-19 are more by 0.02 among fourth grade students. The statistically significant differences reported was seen only between students who sometimes wear masks 0.17 (the highest) and among those students who always wear masks was 0.07 (the lowest), this difference might be related to the higher chance of exposure among those who wear mask infrequently.

The risk estimated in this study among who get two or more vaccines was low (0.068) while the risk of Covid-19 among unvaccinated students or vaccinated with less than 2 doses was high (0.164).

The overall Attack Rate of Covid-19 among the vaccinated students was 12.1%, while the Risk Ratio or Relative Risk estimated was 0.414 (95% CI: (0.183 – 0.936) with a P value 0.026, the association was considered statistically significant.

Conclusions And Recommendations

Although vaccination could not prevent infections but still, they are highly effective against experiencing serious illness and or hospitalization as seen in this study which showed lower risk among vaccinated participants. Therefore, we conclude that medical students should be advised to receive COVID-19 vaccine and to continue practicing the preventive measures since wearing face mask showed lower risk.

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Conflict Of Interest

The authors declared that they have no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this manuscript.

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